

in a laboratory room, Seed viability was checked at monthly intervals by germinating the seeds in water culture at 32°C in the germinator. using 100 seeds and 3 replications.

Seed viability remained high until 352 days from harvest when seeds were stored in metal containers. BR9 germination percentage was highest (see figure). BR8 and BR9 seeds stored in gunny bags lost viability much more rapidly than BR3. A similar trend in seed viability loss was recorded in aus-harvested BR3, BR8, and BR9 seed, except that viability range was shorter for boro-harvested seeds.

It appears that BR8 and BR9 seeds are more susceptible to exposure to the atmosphere (gunny bag storage) although their genetic potential for seed viability range is higher than that of BR3, as indicated by storage in a closed metal container. It is suggested that the seeds of these varieties be carefully stored and handled to minimize exposure to high humidity associated with high temperatures. □

Germination percentage of boro-harvested rice seeds stored in closed metal containers (a) and in gunny bags (b), and mean temperature and mean relative humidity (RH) of storeroom.

Inheritance of leaf sheath color in rice

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We studied the inheritance of purple leaf-sheath coloration using the parents Tai-

chung Native 1 (TN1) with a green leaf sheath, and Dular with a purple leaf sheath, F₁ and F₂ populations of the cross TN1/Dular, and backcrosses of F₁/TN1 and F₁/Dular.

The distributions of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcross progenies are shown in

Table 1. Color varied from deep purple to green. Plants were grouped as colored (purple) and green as shown in Table 2.

The purple leaf sheath was dominant in F₁ and the difference between the two was monogenic. F₂ data also indicated that the purple leaf sheath is dominant and is conditioned by a single gene. The backcross plants of F₁/TN1 confirmed the finding, indicating that a pair of alleles condition segregation in crosses between parents with purple leaf sheaths (Tables 1 and 2). □

Table 1. Distribution of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcross progenies.

Parent or progeny	Plants (no.) in each class					Total plants (no.)
	Purple	Intermediate	dark purple	Light purple	Green	
TN1					60	60
Dular	58					58
F ₁	3		19			22
F ₂	22		128	98	99	347
BC(F ₁ /TN1)	5		27		23	55
BC(F ₁ /Dular)	15		5			20

Table 2. Segregation in F₂ progeny of TN1/Dular, backcross progeny of F₁/TN1 and F₁/Dular for leaf sheath color.

Cross	Plants (no.)			Expected ratio	X ²	P value
	Colored ^a	Green	Total			
TN1/Dular	248	99	347	3:1	2.12	0.20-0.10
F ₁ /TN1	32	23	55	1:1	1.16	0.30-0.20
F ₁ /Dular	20	0	20	No seg.		

^a Colored represents all classes of purple, purple intermediate, dark purple, and light purple.

ERRATUM

T. N. Singh, Gulab Singh, and H. P. Singh. Chemical weed control in dryland rice. IRRN 7 (5) (Oct 1982), 21-22. In the table on page 22, the last row should read:

CD (5%)	0.17	0.20
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